

A thiocyanate based molecular salt as an effective intercalator towards CT DNA

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Abstract : A previously reported thiocyanate based hybrid molecular salt [(dpaH)⁺(NCS)⁻] (**1**) (dpa = 2,2'-dipyridylamine) has been synthesized and structurally characterized. In this work, we have investigated the binding property of this salt with Calf Thymus DNA (CT DNA) using absorption and emission titration, thermal melting studies, viscosity experiments and circular dichroism studies. Binding curves constructed from absorption and emission changes indicate that, the molecular salt displays higher binding affinity ($>10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$) towards DNA. Spectroscopic and hydrodynamic investigations reveal that molecular salt **1** behaves as an effective DNA intercalator.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, spectrofluorimetry, thermal denaturation viscosity measurement, circular dichroism study.

Introduction

Advances in cancer research over the last 20 years has led to the evade conclusion that neoplasia is a malady of genes¹. A large number of malignancies that do not respond to chemotherapy underline the need to develop safe and effective antitumour drugs. DNA is the library of the cell, simultaneously storing and administrating the information required for life. DNA is probably the best structurally characterized biopolymer, thus making it an attractive target for drug design². The design of small molecules that bind and react at specific sequences of DNA becomes important on a molecular level in understanding of how to target DNA sites with specificity. It will lead not only to novel chemotherapeutics but also to a greatly expanded ability for chemists to probe DNA and to develop highly sensitive diagnostic agents. Much attention has focused on the design of organic, DNA binding agents³. Small molecules bind to DNA through several mechanisms : (i) minor/major groove binding; (ii) intercalation and (iii) electrostatic interaction through phosphate backbone. The ability of planar polycyclic aromatic molecules to intercalate, i.e. to be inserted between two consecutive base pairs of DNA, is of special importance since many intercalators are active in antitumor chemotherapy⁴. DNA intercalation was defined by

Mainwaring *et al.* as the sandwiching of a molecule between two adjacent pairs of bases in the DNA double helix. Intercalating molecules are characterised by the possession of an extended electron deficient planar aromatic ring system. Upon binding, they extend and unwind the deoxyribose-phosphate backbone and are stabilised by $\pi\cdots\pi$ stacking interactions with the planar aromatic bases⁵. Some of the classical intercalators are ethidium bromide (EB), acridine orange and doxorubicin. In our previous work⁶ we explored the fluorescence chemosensor property of this molecular salt towards fluoride ion. Now, we have investigated its DNA binding abilities by using electronic absorption spectroscopy, fluorescence spectroscopy, thermal denaturation viscosity measurements and circular dichroism study.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization :

The molecular salt **1** was prepared by the reaction of 2,2'-dipyridylamine (dpa) with ammonium thiocyanate by addition of 20% HCl acid or lanthanide ions at room temperature in methanol-dimethylformamide solution at room temperature. The detailed of synthesis, spectroscopic and crystallographic characterizations have been described in details elsewhere⁶. The ORTEP diagram has been presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. An ORTEP diagram of $[(\text{dpaH})^+(\text{NCS})^-]$ (**1**).

Electronic absorption titration :

The DNA binding experiments of the molecular salt **1** were performed in tris-HCl buffer (50 mM tris-HCl, pH 8.0). The concentration of DNA was determined from the absorption intensity at 260 nm with an ϵ value⁷ of $6600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Absorption titration experiments were made using different concentrations of DNA, while keeping the compound concentration constant.

A broad spectrum in the range 220–340 nm is shown in the UV-Vis spectrum of the molecular salt (Fig. 2). After addition of CT DNA to the solution of **1** in tris-buffer, it is clearly observed that the absorption peak at

Fig. 2. Changes in the electronic absorption spectra of **1** (20 μM) with increasing concentrations (0–25 μM) of CT DNA; the inset shows a fitting of the absorbance data at 267 nm for **1** used to obtain binding constant. $K_b = 4.64 (\pm 0.2) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9905$ for five points).

267 nm undergoes a significant decrease in molecular absorption (hypochromic effect) with small detectable shift (267 to 262 nm) in the absorption wavelength. In hypochromism there is a stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore and the DNA base pairs. After intercalating the base pairs of DNA, the coupling π -orbital is partially filled by electrons and decreasing the transition probabilities. Hence, the gradual decrease in the absorption wavelength indicates strong interaction of **1** with DNA double strand. The binding constant, K_b for the complex has been determined from the plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_F)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ and found to be $4.64 (\pm 0.2) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9905$ for five points) (Fig. 2).

Fluorescence spectroscopy :

The fluorescence spectral method using the standard intercalator ethidium bromide (EB) as a reference was used to determine the relative DNA binding properties of the salt **1** to the CT DNA in tris-buffer (5 mM, pH 8.0). Fluorescence intensities of EB in DNA were measured at different molecular salt concentrations. The addition of **1** to the DNA pretreated with EB causes an appreciable reduction in the fluorescence intensity (Fig. 3) indicating that **1** competes with EB to bind with DNA. The reduction of the emission intensity gives a measure of the DNA binding propensity of the salt and stacking interaction

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of the CT DNA-EB system in tris-HCl buffer based on the titration of **1**. The arrow indicates the increase of the salt concentration; inset represents plot of I_0/I vs $[\text{complex}]$ for the titration of CT DNA-EB system with **1** using spectrofluorimeter; linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant $(K_{sv})_1 = 1.35 (\pm 0.1) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.99804$ for five points).

(intercalation) between adjacent DNA base pairs⁸. The relative binding tendency of the molecule with the CT DNA was determined from the comparison of the slope of the lines in the fluorescence intensity versus complex concentration plot.

The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the molecular salt **1** is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation :

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv} [\text{complex}]$$

where I_0 and I represent the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively. K_{sv} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and [complex], the concentration of the quencher. From the slope of the regression line in the derived plot of I_0/I versus [complex] (Fig. 3), the K_{sv} value for the molecular salt was found to be $1.35 (\pm 0.1) \times 10^5$ ($R = 0.99804$ for five points) indicating a strong affinity of the salt to CT DNA.

Thermal melting studies :

The binding was further tested from optical thermal melting studies⁹. Double stranded CT DNA under the conditions of the experiment had a melting temperature (T_m) of 78 °C (Fig. 4). The melting temperature of the native DNA enhanced in the presence of the salt and at saturation ΔT_m value of 3 °C was observed when the

Fig. 4. Thermal melting profile (relative absorbance change at 260 nm versus temperature) of CT DNA (20 μM) and its complex with molecular salt (D/P = 0.8 and D/P = 2.0).

D/P (DNA/1) ratio is 0.8. The ΔT_m value is 6.5 °C when the D/P ratio is 2.0. Such high stabilization of the DNA helix is essentially due to the strong binding of **1** by intercalation mode.

Hydrodynamic studies :

To further probe and distinguish between a groove binding, intercalative or partial intercalative and groove binding modes, viscosity of the DNA solution was measured in presence of increasing concentrations of **1** and the change in relative viscosities with varying inputs of **1** were estimated¹⁰. Hydrodynamic method provides unequivocal evidence for the mode of binding^{11,12}. The relative specific viscosity of the CT DNA-**1** complex increased steadily as the D/P (drug/DNA molar ratio) increased and ultimately attained saturation at $D/P \geq 1.0$ (Fig. 5). A comparative study was performed with the classical intercalator ETBr. The results favour an intercalation mode of binding of the molecular salt into the double helical organization of the CT DNA.

Fig. 5. Plot of η'_{sp}/η_{sp} versus D/P [DNA/EtBr (●), DNA/molecular salt (■)].

Circular dichroism studies :

The circular dichroism (CD) spectra of the DNA duplex displayed a canonical B-form conformation characterized by a positive band in the 275 nm and a negative band around 248 nm. These bands are caused due to the

stacking interactions between the base pairs and the helical structure of the duplex that provide asymmetric environment for the bases. To record the molecular salt induced changes in the DNA conformation, the CD spectra in the 220–400 nm regions were recorded (Fig. 6) in presence of increasing concentration of **1**. The intensity of the long wavelength positive band decreased in ellipticity as the interaction progressed with a slight red shift

Fig. 6. Representative CD spectra resulting interaction of the molecular salt with CT DNA at pH 8.0 in tris-HCl buffer (50 μM): curves 1–5 denote CT DNA (20 μM) treated with 0, 10, 20, 30 and 40 μM of the molecular salt.

in the wavelength maximum. Moderate changes were also observed in the negative CD band at 248 nm that decreased in ellipticity.

Conclusion

In the present investigation, we have reported the interaction of the molecular salt with CT DNA. The binding constant for the complex is found to be $4.64 (\pm 0.2) \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9905$ for five points). The linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant was determined as $1.35 (\pm 0.1) \times 10^5$ ($R = 0.99804$ for five points). The salt **1** enhanced the thermal stabilization of native DNA by 6 $^\circ\text{C}$ clearly suggesting strong stabilization effects. Visco-

sity measurements provided evidence for intercalation of **1** into the DNA double helix. Conformational changes of DNA within the B-form induced by **1** further testified for the interaction of the molecular salt with double stranded DNA. Overall studies indicate a strong intercalative mode of binding with the CT DNA.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 2,2'-dipyridylamine (Fluka, Germany), ammonium thiocyanate (E. Merck, India) and Calf Thymus DNA (CT DNA) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. The DNA quality and integrity were evaluated using pulsed field gel electrophoresis and visualization after ethidium bromide (EB) staining. All the other reagents and solvents are of analytical grade (A.R. grade) and were purchased from commercial sources and used as received.

Physical measurements :

Ground state absorption was measured with a JASCO V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The fluorescence spectra were recorded on the Fluorometer Hitachi-2000. Absorbance versus temperature profiles (optical melting curves) of DNA and alkaloid-DNA complexes were measured on the Shimadzu Pharmaspec 1700 unit (Shimadzu Corporation, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with the peltier controlled TMSPC-8 model accessory in eight chambered quartz cuvette of 1 cm path length. The viscosity of the DNA-metal complex was determined by measuring the time needed to flow through a Cannon-Manning semi micro size 75 capillary viscometer (Cannon Instruments Company, State College, PA, USA) that was submerged in a thermostated water bath ($20 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Small volumes of the solution of **1** were added to sonicated CT DNA solution placed in the viscometer. The circular dichroism (CD) spectra were recorded on a JASCO J815 spectropolarimeter (Jasco International Co. Ltd., Hachioji, Japan) equipped with a Jasco temperature controller (model PFD 425L/15) interfaced with a HP PC at $20 \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using instrument parameters.

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